

AGILE SELF-ASSESSMENT SURVEY

Scrum Team Level - Practices and Ceremonies	
1	Daily Stand-up
	Held daily, Short (recommended 15min) and focused. (1)
	Held daily, Short (recommended 15min), focused and NOT reporting Status at task level. (2)
	Held daily, Short (recommended 15min), focused and NOT reporting Status at task level with emphasis on value driven delivery with Story completion. (3)
	None of the above (0)
2	Sprint Planning
	Held as a team (1)
	Held as a team with outcome as realistic forecast planning (2)
	Held as a team with outcome as realistic forecast planning focusing on release objectives (3)
	None of the above (0)
3	Sprint Retrospective
	Held at the end of the Sprint (1)
	Held at the end of each Sprint and <5 actions to improve are identified (2)
	Held at the end of each Sprint, <5 actions to improve are identified and are acted upon (3)
	None of the above (0)
4	Sprint Review / Demo
	Held at the end of the Sprint with the whole team (1)
	Held at the end of the Sprint with the whole team and demonstrate working software (2)
	Held at the end of the Sprint with the whole team, demonstrate working software and get feedback from stakeholders (3)
	None of the above (0)
Scrum Team Level - Team Collaboration	
5	Team Collaboration
	Team collaborates every day (1)
	Team collaborates every day outside daily stand-ups (2)
	Team collaborates every day outside daily stand-up and also swarm on stories (3)
	None of the above (0)

6	Delivery - (Average Say-Do Ratio Over Last 3 Sprints)
	Say-Do ratio is below 60% (don't make commitments) or over 140% (under commit and pull stories in) (1)
	Say-Do ratio is between 60% and 80% (make more commitments) or between 120% and 140% (a few under commits) (2)
	Say-Do Ratio is between 80% and 120% (the team is in an ideal, predictable state) (3)
	None of the above (0)
7	Delivery - (Defect rate Ratio Over Last 3 Sprints)
	Defects(Sev 1 and 2) found in the sprint but no plans to resolve all defects.(1)
	Defects(Sev 1 and 2) found in the sprint are resolved (2)
	Defects found in the sprint are resolved and unit test is updated. (3)
	None of the above (0)
8	ScrumMaster
	Facilitates Scrum ceremonies (1)
	Facilitates Scrum ceremonies and removes team impediments (2)
	Facilitates Scrum ceremonies, removes team impediments and helps the team continuously improve themselves (3)
	None of the above (0)
9	Product Owner - Backlog Management
	PO has prioritized backlog (1)
	PO has prioritized backlog and drives sprint backlog grooming/story time (2)
	PO has prioritized backlog, drives sprint backlog grooming/story time and drives release backlog/story time (3)
	None of the above (0)
10	Product Owner Collaboration
	PO Participates in Scrum ceremonies (1)
	PO Participates in Scrum ceremonies and is available for questions/clarifications (2)
	PO Participates in Scrum ceremonies, is available for questions/clarifications, and focuses on value driven delivery (3)
	None of the above (0)
Scrum Team Level - Quality	
11	Unit Testing
	Create unit tests in each sprint for some stories (1)
	Create unit tests in every story in the Sprint (2)

	Write unit tests first for each story and run suit of test with each build. (3)
	None of the above (0)
12	Functional Testing
	Only doing manual functional testing every sprint (1)
	Creating automated functional testing every sprint (2)
	Automated functional tests are run regularly.(3)
	None of the above (0)
13	Continuous Integration - Unit Test Only
	Integrated build per sprint (1)
	Daily commits and automated build passed (2)
	Multiple commits daily and automated builds pass (3)
	None of the above (0)
14	Definition of Done (DoD)
	DoD defined (ideally collaboratively with Team and Mgmt) (1)
	DoD defined and followed in each story, sprint and release (2)
	DoD defined, followed and continuously improved (3)
	None of the above (0)
Release Level	
15	Release Planning
	Held with all delivery teams (1)
	Held with all delivery teams and dependent teams (2)
	Held with all delivery teams and dependent teams. Release planning on regular cadence and widely communicated to external teams. (3)
	None of the above (0)
16	Release Delivery
	Release progress and delivery visible and communicated to internal and external stakeholders (1)
	Release progress and delivery visible and communicated to internal and external stakeholders, and met release goals (2)
	Release progress and delivery visible and communicated to internal and external stakeholders, met release goals, and release predictability (Say-Do Ratio at release level) within +/- 20% (3)
	None of the above (0)
Organizational Level	

17	Impediments
	Organizational impediments escalated and made visible to entire organization (1)
	Organizational impediments resolved <25% of the time (2)
	Organizational impediments resolved between 25-75% of the time (3)
	None of the above (0)
18	Product Vision/Roadmaps
	Have documented product vision and roadmap (1)
	Product vision and roadmap visible, communicated (even changes) (2)
	Product vision and roadmap visible, communicated (even changes) and working toward implementing predictably every release. (3)
	None of the above (0)
19	Quality Improvements
	Measure defect metrics (1)
	Measure and improving defect metrics (2)
	Measure, improving, and have decreasing defect metrics (3)
	None of the above (0)